

The Influence of Parental Behaviour on Adolescent's Emotional Development in the Bamenda II Sub-Division of the North West Region of Cameroon

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to examine "The Influence of Parental Behaviour on Adolescent's Emotional Development in the Bamenda II Sub-Division of the North West Region of Cameroon". The main research objective of the study was to investigate the influence of parental behaviour on adolescent's emotional development. From this research objective emerged three specific objectives. The research objectives were then transformed to research questions and hypothesis. A cross sectional survey research design was used. Questionnaire and an interview guide were used for the collection of data and a purposive and simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. A sample of 150 students was selected and administered the questionnaires while 20 parents were interviewed for the study. Data was analysed quantitatively and qualitatively and descriptive (frequency counts, percentages) and inferential statistics (Chi-Square) were used to analyze the quantitative data while qualitative data was analyzed using thematic analysis. Spearman rho test was used to establish the relationship parental behavior and adolescent's emotional development. The study revealed that, there is a relationship between secure parental attachment and the development of love in adolescents with spearman's rho $r=0.183$ ($P=0.025$), that dictatorial parenting affects the development of anger in adolescents (with spearman's rho $r=0.184$ ($P=0.024$)). It also revealed that parental modeling had an effect on the development of fear in adolescent with spearman's rho $r=0.230$ ($P=0.005$). The findings therefore indicate that, parental behaviour influences adolescent's emotional development. In order to improve on positive parental behaviour, it was recommended that parents should use appropriate child-rearing practices like secure attachment, authoritative, democratic parenting style, and positive modeling styles as these reduce fear and anger development in children and fasten the ability to form future harmonious relationships.

KEYWORDS: Parental behaviour, Adolescent's, Emotional development, parental attachment, parenting style and parental modeling

INTRODUCTION

The emotional development of adolescent influences many attributes of a child's life either positively or negatively and parenting plays a great role on how each child acquires developmentally appropriate emotional skills. Having developmentally appropriate emotional development is crucial to mental health, interpersonal skills, and physical health and is the basis for relationship building. Developing a secure, positive self-esteem, positive interactions with others and control over ones feelings during adolescence is vital to future personality development and emotional development. Adolescent's emotional development is chosen for this study because, adolescence is a period of time when young adolescents seek their own sense of individuality and uniqueness, tend to be moody and restless, they are sensitive and prone to outbursts, vulnerable to emotional pleas and can be easily manipulated (Knowles & Brown, 2000), thus need for the study of adolescent's emotional development.

Parents have significant influence over children's daily interactions and activities, thus it's important to view the implications parental behaviour have on the emotional development of children. Often, parental behaviour is multifaceted, and many parenting practices are typically used in conjunction with one another. The domains of parental behaviour, such as communication style, levels of control, are used in combination with one another to create an individual's overall parental behaviour, thus it is important to take into consideration the overall parenting behaviour when understanding the effects that it has on child outcomes (Pereplechikova & Kazdin, 2005).

Parental behaviour affects how children turn out physically, socially, and emotionally. Parents can help their children develop into emotionally stable people by giving them a supportive environment, positive feedback, role models of

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healthy behaviour and interactions, and someone to talk to about their emotional reactions to their experiences (Ramey & Bristol, 2014). Parental behaviour may influence the development of adolescents some parental behaviours that influence adolescent's emotional development are: parental attachment, parenting style and parental modeling, which have an important role in children's emotional development.

Statement of the problem

When most people think of parenting, they picture providing the child's basic needs like food, clothes and changing diapers, but parenting goes far beyond providing the physical needs of the child. Parents have a significant influence on how children turn out especially as concerns their emotional development and wellbeing. Some parents do not carry out their parental duties effectively, partly due to preoccupation with too many social, cultural, professional, economic and /or financial affairs. As a result children emotional development are neglected due to inadequate time, physical abuse, emotional neglect and confusion by parents in Bamenda II Sub-division. Failure to supply children's basic needs greatly affects the children's emotional development.

Parental behaviour like parental attachment, that has not been inappropriate, most often foul the negative effect, impacts on how the children later in life develops the ability to trust and form intimate relationships. Poor parental behaviour like love withdrawal may lead to psychological difficulties and behaviour problems, such as anxiety or fear. Children of parents who use dictatorian parenting style are more vulnerable to stress, anger and fearful, have problems with regulation and control of negative emotions, hostile aggressive behaviours. The child may develop and display aggressive behaviours as a means of self-protection, and such behaviours may place the child at risk for future status as a bully or victim. It is against this backdrop that the study sought to investigate the influence of parental behaviour on adolescent's emotional development.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the influence of parental behaviour on adolescent's emotional development.

Specific objectives

Specifically, the study was aimed at:

- Finding out the effect of secure parental attachment on the emotional development of adolescent's with emphasis on love.
- Examining the effect of dictatorian parenting on the emotional development of adolescent's with emphasis on anger.
- Investigating the relationship between parental modeling on the emotional development of adolescent's with emphasis on fear.

Literature review

Parental behaviour can be defined as the emotional climate in which parents raise their children (Steinberg, 2001). Parental behaviour is an important requirement for the upbringing of children an especially adolescent which is often accompanied with turbulent crisis (Erikson, 1963). The active role assumed by parents differs from one parent to another. The parental behaviour that children are subjected

to, determines their emotional development. Children develop positive emotions because their parents have provided them with good parental behaviours. Parents being the closest to their children, their behaviour have a lot to play in children's emotional development. This simply means that parental behaviour influences children's emotional development. The child whose parents have showed positive parental behaviour like secure attachment, non over control may develop positive emotions (Arnett, 1999).

The secure parent-child relationship serves as a prototype for future relationships of the child. It is this first relationship that the child uses as a template to apply to future relationship experiences. In short, the qualities of early relationships predict later relationships, and success in later relationships takes root in the context of the parent-child relationship (Gail, 2003). According to Harrison (2003), a secure attachment style generally involves children displaying a strong preference for contact with their primary career. In particular children who have developed a secure attachment can use their career as a safe base from which to explore their world. Securely attached children trust that their career will be there when needed (physical needs) developing a sense of safety, security, reliability, and predictability (emotional and cognitive needs) is developing a good balance of autonomy and returning to their career for comfort when needed.

Research shows that attachment security in adolescence exerts precisely the same effect on development as it does in early childhood: a secure base fosters exploration and the development of cognitive, social and emotional competence (Allen, McElhaney & Land, 2003). Studies of nonclinical samples show that, securely attached adolescents are less likely to engage in excessive drinking, drug use and risky sexual behaviour (Howard & Medway, 2004).

Securely attached adolescents also suffer fewer mental health problems such as anxiety, depression, and inattention, thought problems, conduct disorder, delinquency and aggression (Sund & Wichstrom, 2002). Secure attachment in female adolescents is related to fewer weight-related concerns and less frequent eating disorders, it also predicts more constructive coping skills and significant gains in social skills from 10 to 18 years of age (Allen, Marsh, & McFarland, 2002). Securely attached adolescents manage the transition to high school more successfully; enjoy more positive relationships and experience less conflict with family and peers than do insecurely attached adolescents (Papini, & Roggman, 1992).

Thompson (1999) opined that, securely attached children show greater enthusiasm, compliance, and positive affect (and less frustration and aggression) during shared tasks with their mothers, as well as affective sharing and compliance during free play with their mothers. Securely attached adolescents tend to maintain more harmonious relations with parents. A child that is securely attached will be more than likely to be confident and resilient when confronted with peer pressure. It is believed that secure bonding leads to psychological wellbeing and resistance to ordinary, as well as extreme stress experienced throughout a life time (Thompson, 2000).

Baumrind (1991) studied the continuum of parental control and identifies that, authoritarian parenting make rules and

expect no questioning, punishes misbehaviour (often physically) and parents using these styles tend to be uncommunicative, unresponsive and somewhat distant and they found such children discipline to be withdrawn and anxious. She is of the opinion that this type of parenting generally lead to children who are obedient and proficient, but they rank lower in social competence and self-esteem. They are equally anxious, withdrawn, and unhappy disposition, and have poor reactions to frustration (girls are particularly likely to give up and boys become especially hostile).

According to Lauer & Lawer (1991) in the authoritarian parenting, the approach is to exercise maximum control and to expect unquestioning obedience. Parents here have strict standard and discourage expression of disagreement. Parent child interaction is not the give and take of a developing relationship, but the giving of orders by a superior to a subordinate. In the case of interaction of the rules, discipline is likely to be both severe and physical. In other words, dictatorial parents seek to control their children through ruler. They use rewards and punishment to make their children follow the rules. They give orders and are not likely to explain them. Children raised under this atmosphere perceive their parents as rejecting and as refusing to give them any autonomy. By keeping the focus on pleasing parents, children development of good judgment, problem solving, decision making and reasoning skills are seriously impaired. The force to obey is so strong that there is little room to develop increased behaviour patterns that spring forth from love (Keit, 1984).

Parental modeling of fearful behaviour and avoidant strategies is also likely to increase a child's risk of developing later emotional health problems. An anxious parent may be more likely to model anxious behaviour or may provide threat and avoidant information to their child, increasing the child's risk of anxiety disorder (LeFebvre, 1997). Parents may not be aware of it, but they model behaviours around emotional development, expressivity and food intake beginning when their children are infants. Parents provide very important models by which children learn to express emotions and later learn to control emotional expressivity. For example, researchers have found that children mimic the emotions of their parents (Eisenberg, Fabes, Nyman, Bernzweig, & Pinuelas, 1994). When parents display a wide range of positive and negative emotions in appropriate social contexts, their children are more likely to learn which emotions are appropriate to display in which situations; conversely, when parents display high levels of anger or personal distress, children are less likely to observe and learn appropriate ways to regulate and express their negative emotions (Tibbs, Haire-Joshu & Schechtman, 2001).

Role models are often subjects of admiration and emulation. Through their personal qualities and achievements, they can inspire others to strive and develop without direct instruction. Due to their regular presence and interaction with their children, parents can serve as consistent and evolving role models for their children. Parents serve as role models not only through direct interactions with their children, but through the examples they set with their attitude and behaviour within the family and in the outside world (Salvy, Kieffer, & Epstein, 2007).

Although adolescents spend an increasing amount of time away from home, parents still have much influence on them and are likely to be salient models in their lives. In addition to observing and modeling the actions of others, Bandura also suggested that individuals observe and monitor their own behaviours and derive judgments about these behaviours depending on the responses they elicit from others. These judgments can either result in positive or negative emotional reactions (Zimmerman & Blother, 1979). Parents model for their children how to comfort someone who is crying or smile at someone who is smiling, but other parental behaviors also influence how their children learn to understand the emotions of others (Morris, Steinberg, Myers, & Robinson, 2007).

Emotional development is the emergence of a child's experience, expression, understanding, and regulation of emotions from birth throughout adulthood. It also comprises how growth and changes in these processes concerning emotions occur. Emotional development does not occur in isolation; neural, cognitive, and behavioural development interact with emotional development and social and cultural influences, and context also play a role (Wood, Wood & Boyd, 2004). Erikson (1968) posits emotional development as a series of crises during which individuals must complete arduous, often conflicting tasks in order to maintain a developmental trajectory.

According to the Australian Psychological Association (2012), emotional development is a complex task that begins in infancy and continues into adulthood. The first emotions that can be recognized in children include joy, anger, sadness and fear. Later, as children begin to develop a sense of self, more complex emotions like shyness, surprise, elation, embarrassment, shame, guilt, pride and empathy emerge. Adolescents also have heightened sensitivity to how others evaluate them. Their self-consciousness and the culture-specific nature of guidelines concerning the appropriateness of emotional development and expression make this a particularly difficult time to learn when and how to express or regulate many emotions (Talen, Stephens, Marik, & Buchholz, 2007).

During the period of adolescence, emotions are still developing. In fact, the adolescent years often are considered an emotional period of development. Although adolescents begin to develop independence from their parents and begin to display social signs of independence by gaining employment, driving, and other activities, and their emotional autonomy is represented by conflict and often negative emotions. Some reasons for the negative emotions (like anger and fear) development in adolescents may be due to parental behaviour and cognitive development of abstract thinking abilities. Because adolescents can imagine all sorts of complex and theoretical scenarios for romance or in response to other relationships, they may suffer resulting emotional distress. In turn, social problems become more complex, and adolescents look to their peers to help provide a basis for how to manage the emotions they feel (Halberstadt, Denham, & Dunsmore, 2001).

As adolescents realise that their emotions are separate from their parents' emotions, a process called "emotional autonomy" begins. Adolescents may feel pulled between the close emotional ties they have with their parents and a need

to develop independent emotional responses. If depression is going to occur, it generally begins during adolescence and is more common in girls than in boys (Wood et.al, 2004).

During early adolescence, emotional development is characterized by the quest for independence and identity formation. It is a time when young adolescents seek their own sense of individuality and uniqueness (Knowles & Brown, 2000). They are searching for an adult identity as well as adult acceptance, while striving to maintain peer approval (Kellough & Kellough, 2008). As young adolescents' affiliation base expands to include family and peers, feelings of conflict arise because of competing allegiances. Their search for identity and self-discovery may exacerbate feelings of vulnerability as they become increasingly attuned to the differences between self and others. Typically, the period of early adolescence is intense and unpredictable. Young adolescents have a tendency to be moody, restless, and may exhibit erratic and inconsistent behavior including anxiety, bravado, and fluctuations between superiority and inferiority. They are also often self-conscious, prone to lack self-esteem, and are highly sensitive to criticism of their perceived personal shortcomings (Wiles, Bondi, & Wiles, 2006).

Stroufe, Egeland, Carlson, & Collins (2005) postulated that, a major part of emotional development in children and adolescents is how children recognize, label, and control the expression of their emotions in ways that generally are consistent with cultural expectations. This is called emotional regulation (recognition and delineation of emotions). Children may express negative emotions more often to their mothers than to their fathers because they assume their fathers will react negatively to displays of emotion.

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positively with others. Differences in emotional development result from a child's inborn temperament, cultural influences, disabilities, behaviours modelled by adults, the level of security felt in a child's relationships with adults, and the opportunities provided for social interaction (Halberstadt et.al., 2001).

Fear generally refers to feelings elicited by tangible, realistic dangers. Fear may be provoked by exposure to traumatic situations, observations of other people exhibiting fear, or the receipt of frightening information. Repeated or prolonged exposure to fear can lead to disorders such as combat fatigue, which is characterised by long-term anxiety and other emotional disturbance (Judith, 1994). We don't really know why some fears vanish and others develop into phobias. It appears thoughts, that adult's reactions play a part. Albert, (1977) outline the following ways to curb fear in children;

- Parents should accept fears as normal, offer reassurance, and encourage children to express their feelings freely without being subjected to ridicule or punishment.
- Children should not be allowed, however to avoid what they fear; avoidance simply reinforces the fear.
- Children show fears of both real and imaginary objects and events. Sometimes, these fears develop into phobias, which are irrational, involuntary, and appropriate to the situation. Conditioning and modeling can help children overcome fears and phobias.
- Reduce exposure to frightening stories in books and on TV until the child is better able to distinguish between appearance and reality. Make a thorough "search" of the child's room for monsters, showing him that none are there. Leave a night-light burning, sit by the child's bed until he falls asleep.

Malatesta, Zander & Haviland (1982) stated that, anger produces more muscle tension, higher blood pressure, and a lower heart rate. Anger is attributed to the secretion of adrenalin and another hormone, noradrenalin. Other physical signs of anger include scowling, glumming, twitching. The most common cause of anger in children, for example, is restraint of activity. Children commonly become angry due to restrictive rules or demands, lack of attention by parents, or failure to accomplish a task. As children reach late adolescence and adulthood, the primary sources of anger shift from physical constraints and frustrations to social ones (Allyn & Bacon, 2000). In adolescents and adults, the basis of anger include disapproval, deprivation, exploitation, manipulation, betrayal, and humiliation, and the responses to it become less physical and more social with age. Physical violence does occur in young adolescents, but in most situations it is avoided in deference to social pressures (Gnepp, Jackie, & Hess, 1986).

Fuller (1734) cited in Myers, (1992) stipulated that when children are angry, they turn to be violent and even behave as mad people. This is why he says that, Anger is said by the sages to be a "short madness" that "carries the mind away" and can be "many times more hateful than the injury that caused it". William Shakespeare (1616) cited in Myers, (1992) agrees that, "noble anger", "makes any coward brave" and "bring back his strength".

Luhn, & Rebecca (1992) outlined a number of defense mechanisms to deal with anger.

- Practise denial, refusing to recognise that they are angry. Such repressed anger often finds another outlet, such as a physical symptom.
- Another way of circumventing anger is through passive aggression, in which anger is expressed covertly in a way that prevents retaliation. Both sarcasm and chronic lateness are forms of passive aggression. In the classroom, a passive aggressive student will display behaviour that is subtly uncooperative or disrespectful but which provides no concrete basis for disciplinary action. Passive aggressive acts may even appear in the guise of a service or favor, when in fact the sentiments expressed are those of hostility rather than altruism.

Myer (1992) said that love sees but the good in others and appreciates it. This is supported by Aristotle who defined love as “to will the good of another”. Thus, warm parental behaviour evokes this positive emotion of love in children. Fehr, & Russell, (1991) posits that, love is an attitude held by one person towards another, involving a predisposition to think, feel, and behave in certain ways towards that person. Love is focused on behaviours such as shared activities, disclosing intimacies, and so on.

Aquinas (2010) stipulated that, love is not something that is simply understandable. It is a feeling of the heart which one can only observe practically. Most Basic Need: Feeling Loved: the most fundamental need of the adolescent, is to feel emotional love from the significant adults in his life. Love has consequences for health and well-being. Joyful activities such as love activate areas in the brain responsible for emotion, attention, motivation and memory, and it may further lead to reduction of cortisol, which reduces stress (Lewis, Thomas, Amini, & Lannon, 2000).

Johnson & Tversky, (1983) cited in Myers, (1992) opines that, when an adolescent has the feeling that he/she is not being loved by others especially caregivers, their mood becomes gloomy, life as a whole seems depressing but when they feel loved, their mood brightens, their relationships, self-image, their hopes for the future seem promising. The emotion love makes us feel happy and when we are happy we are more willing to help others. People with this positive emotion develop a mood-boosting experience, such as succeeding on challenging task, or recalling that they possess this positive emotion, they develop properly and are become balanced individual in the society (Wood et.al, 2004).

Theoretical framework

According to Erikson (1968) in his psychosocial theory, each person experiences eight “psychosocial crises” which help to define his or her growth and personality. Each stage of life has its own “psychosocial” task, each of which is defined by conflicts involving the individual’s relationship with the social environment, which must be resolved satisfactorily in order for healthy development to occur. According to Erikson’s theory, the way a person resolves the crisis will determine their personal identity and future development. Adolescents resolve two life crises. The first crisis typically occurs during early to middle adolescence, and is called the crisis of identity versus identity confusion and the second crisis, occurring between late adolescence and early adulthood, is called the crisis of intimacy versus isolation.

Erikson believed that when youth successfully navigate this crisis they emerge with the ability to form honest, reciprocal relationships with others and have the capacity to bond with others to achieve common goals (e.g., marriage). If youth do not resolve this crisis, their emotional development becomes stalled, and as a result, they will remain isolated and lonely without social supports.

Bandura (1977) in his Social learning theory posits that, people learn from one another via observation, imitation and modeling. People learn through observing others’ behaviour, attitudes, and outcomes of those behaviours. Children model can be their parents and children go a long way to pick characteristics from several different models, whom they choose on the basis of how much powers a person seems to have and how nurturing, or caring, the person is. Bandura’s theory emphasises that for effective modeling to take place the following processes most take into play: attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation.

According to Bowlby (1969) in his “Attachment theory”, the first bond in the child’s life becomes the base from which all other relationships are formed. It addresses how human beings respond within relationships when hurt, separated from loved ones, or perceiving a threat. The most important tenet of attachment theory is that children need to develop a relationship with at least one primary caregiver for the child’s successful social and emotional development, and in particular for learning how to effectively regulate their feelings.

Baumrind (1971) developed the theory that there were four main types of parenting styles and that difference in parenting styles accounted for the way children functioned socially, emotionally and cognitively. Baumrind identified four parenting styles: authoritative, authoritarian, permissive-indulgent and permissive-uninvolved. These parenting styles thus represent a picture of typical and widespread ways of parenting.

Methods

The research design adopted for this study was the cross sectional survey research design. Sample was made up of 170 respondents; 20 parents and 150 students were used for the study were in the 150 students were the adolescents that responded to the questionnaire and the 20 parents were the respondents interviewed. The parents were purposively selected and the simple random sampling technique was used to select the adolescents. It enabled the researcher to include a range of people in the sample that provided data through the use of various instrument.

The data derived from the research was quantitative and qualitative; as such quantitative and qualitative methods of data analyses were employed in analysing the data collected. Interviews and the open-ended questions were analyzed using the process of thematic analysis whereby concepts or ideas were grouped under umbrella terms or key words. As for the quantitative data, inferential statistics was used using frequency and proportions and Multiple Response Analysis to aggregate responses within conceptual components. Chi-Square test was used to compare proportions for significant difference. The effect of secure parental attachment, dictatorial parenting, and parental modelling on the emotional development of adolescents was measured using

Spearman’s Rho Correlation test because all the variables violated the normality assumption at the 0.05 level (Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests for normality: $P < 0.05$). In fact, these tests of normality verify the null hypothesis that the real distribution of the data does not

depart significantly from the theoretical assumed normal distribution. The null hypothesis is expected to be accepted if the normality assumption is not violated therefore giving room for a parametric test to be used, but it was not the case for this study.

Findings

Secure parental attachment on the emotional development of adolescents

Table1 Distribution of adolescent’s view on secure parental attachment

Statements	Response Options		
	Always	Sometimes	Never
My parents protect me from danger	14.7% (22)	14.7% (22)	.7% (1)
I experience less conflict with family members and friends	34.0% (51)	58.0% (87)	8.0% (12)
My parents spend their leisure time with me by telling me stories	36.0% (54)	54.7% (82)	9.3%(14)
My parents play with me	32.7% (49)	61.3% (92)	6.0%(9)
My parents discuss pleasant issues related to life with me	56.0% (84)	38.7% (58)	5.3%(8)
My parents provide me love, security and all my needs	79.3% (119)	20.0% (30)	.7% (1)
MRS	53.38% (484)	41.2%(371)	5.0% (45)

The Multiple Response Set (MRS) showed that, majority of the adolescents 53.38% always feel secure parental attachment. They were the most satisfied with the fact that their parents provide them with love, security and all their needs 79.3% (119), that their parents discuss pleasant issues related to their life with them 56.0% (84), that their parents spend their leisure time with them by telling them stories 36.0% (54), the fact that they experience less conflict with their parents 34.0% (51) and the least been the fact that their parents protect them from danger 14.7% (22).

Dictatorian parenting on the emotional development of adolescents with emphasis on anger

Table2 Adolescents view of dictatorian parenting

Statements	Response Options		
	Always	Sometimes	Never
My Parents are strict on me	40.0% (60)	59.3% (89)	.7%(1)
I am beaten by my parents when I do something wrong	30.0% (45)	64.0% (96)	6.0% (9)
My parents make all rules at home, and expect no questioning	42.0% (63)	49.3% (74)	8.7% (13)
My parents impose their decisions on me.	36.0% (54)	58.7% (88)	5.3% (8)
My parents don’t allow my friends to visit me at home.	29.3% (44)	54.0% (81)	16.7% (25)
My parents shout or scold at me when I misbehave	52.0% (78)	44.0% (66)	4.0% (6)
MRS	38.2%(344)	54.9%(498)	6.9% (62)

Only very few adolescents indicated not to have ever experience dictatorian parenting with a proportion of 6.9%.The type of dictotarian parenting they experienced the most and always was the fact that, their parents shout at them when they misbehave 52.0% (78), the fact that their parents make all rules at home and expect no questioning 42.0% (63), followed by parents being strict at them 40.0% (60), parents imposing their decision on them 36.0% (54), parents beating them when they do something wrong 30.0% (45) and lastly do not allow their friends to visit them at home 29.3% (44).

Parental modeling on the emotional development of adolescents with emphasis on fear

Table3 Table: Adolescents view on parental modeling

Statements	Response Options		
	Always	Sometimes	Never
I learn when I interact with my parents.	70.7% (106)	26.0% (39)	3.3% (5)
I avoid the things that my parents don’t like	66.7% (100)	30.7% (47)	2.7% (4)
My parents set good examples for me to follow like cautioning me against bad company	84.7% (127)	13.3% (20)	2.0% (3)
I am always worried about my parents’ anger	63.3% (95)	30.0% (45)	6.7% (10)
My parents like quarreling and fighting at home	14.7% (22)	29.3% (44)	56.0% (84)
My parents drink too much alcohol	9.3% (14)	18.7% (28)	72.0% (108)
MRS	51.6%(464)	24.7%(222)	23.8(214)

The Multiple Response Set (MRS) shows that 464 (51.6%) of students said that, their parents always model things to them in one way or another. Also, (222)24.7% students indicate parents sometimes model behaviours to them. Fewer adolescents, 214(23.8%) said their parents never model behaviours to them.

Figure1: Model of adolescent's and parent's view on parental behaviour and emotional development

The conceptual diagram figure 1 painted from qualitative analysis reveals that parents and adolescents indicated caring, motivation, spending time, provision of needs, beating, restriction, scolding, non-caring influences emotional development in adolescents.

Discussions

Secure parental attachment on the emotional development of adolescent's with emphasis on love

There was a positive effect between secure parental attachments on the emotional development of adolescent's. This is because majority of the adolescents always feel secure parental attachment as they are happy when their parents spend time with them, providing their needs, showing them concern and being available. Again majority of the parents interviewed said they make their children

develop love by "providing their needs, spending time with them, caring for them". This tie with the view of Kestenbaum, Farber & Sroufe (1989) who stipulated that, both the quality of care and security of attachment affect children's later capacity of empathy, emotional development and regulation, cognitive development, and behavioural control. Again, Ainsworth, Blehar, Walters & Wall (1978) supported this view as they opined that, securely attached children used their mothers as a secure base form to explore and are able

to separate from them to go off and investigate their surroundings and such children are cooperative and free from anger.

Dictatorian parenting on the emotional development of adolescents with emphasis on anger

The findings of the study showed that dictatorian parenting does have an influence on the adolescent's emotional development and majority of the adolescents revealed that their parents are dictatorian on them since, they sometimes beat, scold, give strict rules and impose decisions on them and this makes them to develop anger. Most of the interviewees revealed that, they guide their children by "scolding them, beating, giving firm rules" This is in line with Lauer & Lawer (1991) who stated that in the authoritarian parenting, parents have strict standard and discourage expression of disagreement and that dictatorian parents seek to control their children through rules. They use punishment to make their children follow the rules. They give orders and are not likely to explain them.

Parental modeling on the emotional development of adolescents with emphasis on fear.

The study revealed that parental modeling has an influence on the emotional development of adolescents therefore implying that the more the parents model behaviours to adolescents the more they develop fear. The findings of the research show that students said that their parents always model things to them in one way or another and parents equally said their adolescents emulate behaviours they exhibit. This is in conformity with LeFebvre (1997) who discovered that, parental modeling of fearful behaviour and avoidant strategies is also likely to increase a child's risk of developing later emotional health problems. An anxious parent may be more likely to model anxious behaviour or may provide threat and avoidant information to their child, increasing the child's risk of anxiety disorder.

Recommendations

- Parents of young adolescents should engage in authoritative parenting practices to assist in the growth and development of their child's emotional development. When parents engage in parenting practices that set high standards and expectations, yet listen and encourage independence, the children tend to show higher levels of positive emotional development than those childrearing styles of permissive or authoritarian.
- Appropriate child-rearing practices like secure attachment, authoritative, democratic parenting style and positive modeling styles should be adopted by parents of adolescents as these reduce fear and anger development in children and fasten the ability to form future relationships.
- Young adolescent's environments should be free from harsh criticism, humiliation, and sarcasm because with regard to emotional development, young adolescents need opportunities that allow them to play out their emotions as well as promote self-assessment.

Conclusions

This study concludes that parental behaviour affects adolescent's emotional development. This study has empirically investigated the effect of secure parental attachment, examined the effect of dictatorian parenting and

investigated the relationship between parental modeling on the emotional development of adolescents. It was evidently proven that these variables affect adolescent's emotional development in one way or the other. Parents no matter their educational background, occupation and age still have a role to play in adolescent's emotional development.

In trying to compare parents view and adolescents view on parental behaviour and adolescents development, the researcher found out that, adolescents develop emotions depending on their parents behaviour like being available or providing attachment schemes, the methods the use to discipline their children or the behaviours they model will determine adolescents development of the emotions love, fear and anger. Parents therefore have as paramount responsibility to provide the child with all the support and care needed to function properly. If adolescents are being provided with all the love, provision of their physical, emotional and cognitive needs, being available when they need assistance, using authoritative or holistic parenting style, modeling positive behaviours, adolescents will certainly develop positive emotions which will enable them to fit squarely in an ever changing society.

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